

Restoring French Language Teaching In Public Primary Schools In Nigeria For International Integration

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Abstract

The issue of the teaching of French language in public primary schools has continued to generate positive criticisms channeled towards restoring the situation. Teaching of French in primary schools in Nigeria became official through the development of primary school curriculum for French in 2007, but since then, the impact is felt only in some major private schools and establishments. Our study based in Imo State for generalization, revealed that there are no public primary schools doing French but there are several French teachers in these schools teaching other subjects. Also, most of these teachers are enthusiastic about reviving the teaching and learning of French in public primary schools. This study therefore showed the need and recommended the implementation of the primary school French in the public schools, believing that the reestablishment of the teaching of French in public primary schools can positively influence French studies and bring about international integration.

Keywords: International, Integration, French

Introduction

Our preliminary enquiry in public primary schools in Imo State, and indeed Nigeria, for a general view, has revealed that for some times now, it is only in the major private schools that the teaching and learning of French is carried out. French does not feature as one of the

teaching subjects even though there is an existing primary school curriculum for French. (French Language for Primary 4-6). Even, in the said private primary schools where French is taught, we usually find one or two French teachers and in most cases the teaching is abandoned once the teacher retires, gets transferred or quits teaching. Such a situation

makes mockery of French language teaching and learning such that the impact is not felt, while the existing curriculum seems forgotten or not in existence. The general idea is that French does not exist in the public primary schools where a lot of the head-teachers are not bothered about it.

The Federal government of Nigeria through the National Policy on education wishes Nigerians to speak French, but how do we establish and show the importance of teaching and learning of French in basic schools in Nigeria to introduce and encourage basic studies of the language and to achieve its *raison d'être* in the nation? Thus, this paper is a contribution to the several reasons for reviving French in public primary schools. Precisely, this study intends to point out the importance and the need to revive teaching and learning in public primary schools and to put emphasis on the implementation of the primary French curriculum in Nigeria, using Imo State as a case study. Furthermore, this study addressed such questions as:

1. Of what value is French language teaching and learning in Nigerian public primary schools to teacher formation institutions?
2. Can the existing primary school French curriculum be adequately implemented?
3. In what ways can public primary school French restoration bring about national or international integration to Nigeria?

Review of Relative Literature

Primary school and French in Nigerian:

Primary school or primary education, in many countries of the world is the first degree of teaching that the child receives. Primary school provides mostly the learning of reading, writing and basic calculations or arithmetic. Generally, children begin primary school towards the age of 6 and finish up towards the age of 11 (education. gov.fr 2018) According to Wikipedia (2018) "Primary education and elementary education is typically the first stage of formal education, coming after preschool and before secondary education. Primary education usually takes place in a primary school or elementary school". Therefore, primary education is the foundation upon which all other formal education of the individual in a given society is based. In their own view point, Asodike and Ikpitibo (2014) noted that primary education is the essential part of the hierarchy of the educational system of any given country. It offers the young

learners the fundamental knowledge for writing, reading and calculations, as well as technologies, techniques and skills necessary to integrate them into their societies.

In France, primary education include: Nursery school, from 3years (Sometimes 2) to 6 years (schooling at this stage is not compulsory); elementary school from 6 years to 11 years (schooling is compulsory and can take place at home or at the school). Primary school receives and trains children from 6 to 11 years. It is mix and free if it is a public school. In Nigeria, the same condition applies and primary school period remains six years. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN 2014), the objectives for the establishment of primary schools include:

- a. To inculcate permanent literacy, numeracy and the ability to communicate effectively;
- b. To lay a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking;
- c. To give citizenship education as a basis for effective participation in and contribution to the life of the society;
- d. To mould the character and develop sound attitude and morals in the child;
- e. To develop in the child the ability to adapt to his changing environment;

- f. To give the child opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable him to function effectively in the society within the limits of his capacity;
- g. To provide the child with basic tools for further educational advancement including preparation for trades and crafts of the locality.

To achieve these objectives, the federal government declared primary education compulsory but free under the Universal Basic Education (UBE) introduced on the 30th September 1999 by the former President Olusegun Obasanjo (Abdurahim and Njoku 2015: 122). Two of the aims of the UBE Act (2004) include: *To develop awareness and appreciation of the potentials of other Nations and the international community for exchange of world views; and, to develop aesthetic values and appreciation of oneself and other peoples' culture.* It is in pursuance of this that major innovations in the primary school came into being, like management under private schools, structural organization, curriculum relevance, teaching methods etc. (Izuagba and Ogbonnaya, 2017:182-184) The primary school curriculum for instance comprises such subjects as: *Languages: Language of immediate environment, English, French and Arab. Other subjects such as : Mathematics,*

Science, Physical and Health education, religious knowledge, agriculture, home economics, social studies and citizenship education, cultural and creative arts such as drawing, handicraft, music and other cultural activities (FRN, 2014).

It is based on the fact that French is one of the recommended subjects in both secondary and tertiary institutions that the study of French in Nigerian primary school became matter of necessity. According to Kim (2016) the teaching of French became official in primary school in 2007 following the production of a curriculum - French language for Primary 4-6 - by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC). But for the past years, only private and some federal characterized establishments were teaching this language because they were the only schools that respect and put into practice the declarations of the government on French. Unfortunately, majority, if not all the public primary schools of today have never taught French as a subject, despite recent pronouncements and language policies in favour of the teaching of French. It is even at this level that the study ought to be compulsory if the government is to live up to her pronouncements, as we can see here:

..... It would be recalled that the administration of former Head of State General Sani Abacha made the learning of French language compulsory in both primary and junior secondary schools in Nigeria. This in effect covers the 9 years of free and compulsory learning at the basic level of education. The current 9-year basic education curriculum provides for the compulsory study of French language at the middle and upper levels of basic education which begins from primary four and ends at the third and final year of junior secondary school. (dailytrust.com, 2016)

In general, primary education serves to initiate and introduce knowledge more or less generalized. Therefore, as it is rather an initiative teaching. Kim (2016) notes that in initiative teaching, one necessarily finds out the objectives of sensitization, but it is more appropriate to see initiative teaching as true learning. This is more or less in conformity with Nigerian children for them to communicate in foreign languages right from their young age. Countries like Luxembourg, Finland, Italy, etc introduce second or third languages in the primary school. Educational psychologists and theorists have shown that the child is capable of learning several

languages at the same time and at the same level and children who started earlier the study of foreign languages understand their maternal language better, having become conscious of the existence of language as a phenomenon. (Amadi, 2015) Thus PushPinder and Jindal, (2014:22) noted that ‘Psycholinguistics is concerned with the learning of language at various stages: the early acquisition of a first language by children and later stages in acquisition of first and other languages.’ There are other theories on this factor. By theory, we understand an explanatory schema or a referential plan that give an understanding to identified phenomena.

Education Theory: For the purpose of our study, we emphasize on the humanist theory of education that expounds on idea of education for all. This theory is based on the idea according to which the human nature is fundamentally good. Each individual is unique, all humans are born equal and that the inequalities that arise among the beings are the products of circumstances. Kant (1989) one of the well known theorists emphasized that the aim of education is to develop in each individual all the perfection he is capable of. If the study of French language in the Nigerian context is deemed necessary for a full achievement of the Nigerian child later in life, then the primary school French curriculum

should be well implemented. Messi (2010) in his point of view also stated that education consists of a methodical socialization of the young generation. This socialization starts right from birth, within the family, but certainly, it is at the school that it is systematized and operationalized such that the school is seen as a central place for social continuity as regards the transmission of values, norms and knowledge. In the same vein, Dewy (1990:16) believed that the school in the first instant is a social institution. Education being a socializing process, the school is simply this form of community in which resides all the learning activities geared towards effectively bringing the child to benefit from the values inherent in his race and to use his personal capabilities in dealing with social matter.

Nigeria is plurilinguistic in her nature and this encourages bilingualism and multilingualism. Krashen (2017) an American linguist postulated that one ought to learn a second language the same way he learnt his mother tongue. To support his postulation, he gave out five hypothesis of theory of natural language study as thus:

- **The Acquisition Cycle Hypothesis:** One learns a second or other languages like the way he learnt the first one, in

a way he is unconscious of it, without stress or effort.

- **Conscious Cycle Hypothesis:** The conscience serves to control the quality of oral and written productions. This conscious and voluntary learning in adults is fulfilled in the child through the surrounding of his mother tongue.
- **The Natural Order Hypothesis:** Language mastering starts with oral comprehension. Expression follows gradually from easy to difficult ones. Finally, comes writing of which more complex grammatical structures are discovered and re-used.
- **The Input Hypothesis:** To master well a second language, language acquisition tasks should be slightly little above the level of the learner, being neither too above him nor too below him.
- **The Affective Domain Hypothesis:** Motivation, self confidence and most generally, emotions, have a major role in the acquisition of a second language. Learning through the topics in which one is interested in or one is very familiar within the mother tongue, makes the understanding and learning of the second language more motivating, easier and faster.

Thus, these theories and hypothesis, if tactfully applied in the teaching of French as a foreign language in the primary school will keep most children at ease with the subject and French will actually feature like any other subject learnt in the primary school such that at the secondary level, more students would be found studying French and creating more awareness and preparations for the tertiary level. Teachers who studied French but are teaching other subjects will live up to their expectations in the field of their study. Therefore if in the present situation the entire subjects listed in the National Policy on Education for primary school are all taught in the public schools, why then is French omitted? Does the study of French encumber the study of other subjects and language of study in the primary school? No.

Primary School French Curriculum: The curriculum is considered to be a plan of educative actions, what students should be made to know, understand and be able to do in each subject and at each school level. For Ferreira (2017), a curriculum is the total actions planned to suscite instruction. It comprises the defined objectives of the teaching, the contents, methodology (including evaluation), materials (including textbooks) and all the dispositions relative to adequate training of the teachers. According to

edu.tech/wiki (2017), curriculum designs the conception, the organization and the programming of teaching/learning activities in line with educational perspectives. It encompasses the statement of objectives, contents, activities and learning procedures as well as modalities and evaluation strategies to assess students. Its conception is the echo of a school project reflecting a societal project; it gives place to behaviours and practices rooted in a given educational reality.

In the opinion of Asodike and Ikpitibo (2018), educational reforms in the whole world are gradually being based on the curriculum as the pressure of education has the goal of achieving the values of the society, by reflecting it in the content of the curriculum. The objective of these changes is to ensure total development of the learner. This point of view is shared by Izuagba and Ogbonnaya (2017:40 - 41)) when they said: “

Curriculum simply means all planned learning experiences and guided outcome formulated for the learner's personal and social competencies. The needs of the society are always covered by the curriculum. Curriculum considers the learner's needs and that is why it is reviewed regularly to meet current challenges.

Thus curriculum is broad and covers everything the learner should learn.

For Nigerian government to achieve its dream about French learning, the ministry of education through the NERDC produced a primary school curriculum in 2007, revised in 2012. According to Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2012), the curriculum covers the 3 last years of study of French (4, 5 and 6) in the primary school. Each year is divided into three terms with three themes and sub-themes, topics (Actes de paroles) under each sub-theme and well defined communicative objectives. Odizuru (2016) notes that:

There is need for conformity in the implementation of the French curriculum; this is because at the moment some states are not encouraging the teaching/learning of French language in their schools. Even where French is supposed to be taught, some school heads discourage their trained French language teachers from teaching the subject. Instead, such teachers are compelled to teach other subjects such as English, Nigerian languages, etc .As a result, in such schools, French is not allowed on the time-table. Maybe inspectors need to be appointed and

instructed to visit schools to enforce the teaching of French language in such schools. In the same vein, school owners should build more classrooms to decongest the over bloated number of students and recruit more teachers so that the aims of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) could be achieved.

All the planning of the school curriculum together with its teaching/learning are all based on different adequate theories. As Ikpeazu (2006:15) has put it, the psychology of education helps pedagogists to develop a specific and suitable curriculum for individuals in different educational levels and based on the needs of the society. Iteogu (2016) noted that:

The issue of language curriculum development can hardly be thorough and effective if considered outside the context of national educational objectives. Hence, there is the need for a co-ordinate French language curriculum within the context of a Nation's Policy on Education. With this in mind, it is necessary for us to examine some of the key institutions charged with the French language

curriculum development and implementation at the different levels.

Thus, the primary French curriculum is a working document that if well implemented will not only create the much needed awareness for the teaching of French, but will also lead to the much desired impact for many Nigerians to speak French thereby encouraging the use of French as Nigeria's second official language after English

Empirical Studies: we have noted the same view point expressed by Legrand (1996) from his experience in Paris in the past long years. This concrete, practical, lucid and clear contribution, even though it has taken place for a long period of time now, still fits in our contemporary context, a period where the need for a reform is glaringly staring at us as well as the need for new structures and development. In several debates and discussions on how to "revolutionize" the methodology of our teaching, Legrand (1996) believed in the movement of reflex and analysis that once more revive the principles, methods, programmes, efficiency and productivity, that is the purpose of our national education.

As for Asodike and Ikpitibo (2016) their research on "Basic Issues in Primary Education Delivery in Nigeria" actually and very well analyzed the functionality of primary

education in Nigeria. No doubt primary education is the panacea to resolving such problems like ignorance, illiteracy, religious crises, insecurity and political servitude. Therefore the strength of primary education depends on what we have ordinarily taken to be basic education with the sole objectives of equipping the young ones with the tools they need to enquire, think, conclude and understand events and the world around them. As for these researchers, the fundamental components in the management of primary education in Nigeria essentially include: its functionality, structural changes, student's enrolment, financing, infrastructure, personnel and the curriculum. A very important function of the primary education is to provide communicative skills capable of providing the students with social and economic empowerment for the development of the nation. This is achieved through knowledge of the basic reading, writing and arithmetic skills.

Approach and Methodology of the Work:

This work was done with the qualitative method and approach in researching, to enquire on the necessity of implementing the primary school French and reviving French in public primary schools in Imo State, in Nigeria

for international integration. Imo State is one of the states of the south eastern states of Nigeria, surrounded by Anambra, Enugu, Abia and Rivers State. Imo State is compromised of three education zones: Okigwe, Orlu and Owerri. According to our data from Imo State Universal Basic Educational Board, Owerri (IMSUBEB, 2018), there are 1,280 public primary schools in Imo State and 14,453 teachers constituted of 1,346 males and 13,107 females.

Data Collection:

Most of our information was gathered through data collected from the Universal Basic Education Board of Imo State, Owerri as well as oral interview with its staff and other personnel, Headmasters and Headmistresses of public primary schools met during several meetings held at Hero's Square, International Convention and Conference Centre (ICCC), Local Government Headquarters, Teachers House etc. all in Imo State.

Below are tables showing the distribution of public primary schools in each Local Government Area of the three educational zones in Imo State:

Orlu Zone

N	Local Government Area	Number of public primary School
1	Oru East	53
2	Orsu	42
3	Ohaji Egbema	59
4	Oguta	46
5	Nwangele	28
6	Isu	22
7	Ideato South	44
8	Ideato North	62
9	Nkwerre	15
10	Njaba	33
11	Orlu	57
12	Oru West	36
Total		497

Okigwe Zone

N	Local Government Area	Number of public primary School
1	Ihitte Uboma	31
2	Obowo	35
3	Ehime Mbano	58
4	Okigwe	58
5	Onuimo	34
6	Isiala Mbano	64
Total		280

Owerri Zone

N	Local Government Area	Number of public primary School
1	Aboh Mbaise	58

2	Ngor Okpuala	81
3	Ahiazu Mbaise	48
4	Ezinihitte Mbaise	52
5	Ikeduru	64
6	Mbaitoli	81
7	Owerri West	44
8	Owerri Municipal	26
9	Owerri North	49
Total		503

Source of Data: IMSUBEB, OWERRI, 2018

From the table above, there are 1280 public primary schools. Out of this population, we randomly selected 432 from the 3 educational zones: 132 schools from Orlu, 178 schools from Owerri and 122 from Okigwe. This provided us with 432 head teachers with whom we discussed and interviewed orally to ascertain the place of the teaching and learning of French in Imo State public primary schools. The meetings for the interview and discussions were facilitated by the several rendezvous organized for the Head teachers at the Hero's Square, ICCC, NUT/Teacher's house, and Local Government headquarters.

Data Analysis and Discussions:

Following the oral interview of the head teachers and some teachers in the primary schools, we were able to note that:

- Presently, French is taught in none of the public primary schools.
- There is an existing primary school French curriculum but not found in the schools but at the school board.
- There are several primary school teachers who studied French, but they do not teach it in their schools.
- The teachers are generally enthusiastic about the idea of teaching French as a subject in their respective schools.
- Several Head teachers are indifferent about re-introducing French in the time table. To them, if the state government initiates it and is instrumental to the implementation by providing enough teachers, they

have no objections as it will stand like any other school subject.

In the general case and also according to our findings, particularly as it regards points 1, 2 and 5 above, despite the fact that French is the second official international language of Nigeria, we do not teach French in the public primary schools in Imo State. Even up till now, the federal government is still insisting on the importance of French studies in the country, but at the implementation level of the declarations made in favour of French learning/teaching, we do not have practical activities in schools. Thus as noted in dailytrust.com (2016):

But beyond this public proclamation is the need for government to back the statement with necessary policies clearly spelt out in the country's National Policy on Education especially as it concerns senior secondary and tertiary institutions. The policy already exists for lower level schools. At the tertiary level, it could be added to the existing group of General Studies courses which students are required to pass as requisite conditions for graduating from any tertiary institution in Nigeria. This strategic policy in its new form will equally sustain the interest of students in their study of

French language over a long period of time.

In discussing points 3 and 4 of our findings, we saw that the teachers who read French are not happy teaching other subjects. They teach because they just have to work. This is very similar to the observation made by Osemeke (2015:20) who stated that:

It is regrettable that a greater percentage of government schools do not teach French. More sanding is the fact that most states and local governments, in their desire to promote English and other languages compel French teachers to teach English or other subjects other than French. This has not only discouraged the French teacher but negates the spirit of the policy and gradually tends to eliminate French studies in such communities.

Apart from the school teachers met, many people would like French to be re-introduced to the primary schools but lack of French teachers is a major militating factor. This factor not only affects the primary school level, but also the secondary schools. This is not surprising as at the tertiary level, especially at Colleges of Education where French teachers are to be produced, you only see a handful of students (both for NCE and Degree programmes) studying French. Since

these students, especially the NCE products are not absorbed in schools after their training; students find it difficult to enroll in the departments of French.

We note for instance that in Imo State, the department of French of Alvan Ikoku Federal

College of Education, Owerri ought to be producing enough teachers, at least from the NCE programme to address the issue of lack of French teachers, but unfortunately the number of students in training diminishes every year. Below is an enrolment table of the department for the past 5 years.

Enrolment for last 5 years (French Dept. AIFCE, Owerri)

Year	NCE	B.A/ Ed	Sandwich NCE	Sandwich BA/Ed	Weekend/Evening programme
2017	5	10	1	1	2
2016	4	9	-	2	1
2015	2	11	2	3	-
2014	27	9	2	3	-
2013	44	5	2	3	-

Year: May, 2018

French for National and International Integration

Generally, French as an official language can serve as a lingua franca in Nigeria like the English counterpart. Although within the nation, its impact is less felt, it serves more at the international scene. According to Amadi (2016:217) *“Foreign languages are taught in order to encourage an empathetic understanding of other nations and cultures.... The introduction of a foreign idiom into the child’s world helps develop tolerance towards people who are different, and in the long run*

contributes towards international understanding.” Considering the general role of the language in international organizations, it has helped Nigeria to participate fully and integrate with world affairs.

Bilateral relations between Nigeria and France have not only made the two countries to relate well but have also fostered and sustained French studies in Nigeria such that Nigerians who studied French carry certain French activities in unison regardless of ethnic and cultural differences. Once in Diaspora in particular, Nigerians usually see themselves as

brothers and sisters, but more to those that studied French as they easily integrate into the francophone world in whatever geographical location they find themselves.

The three Centers for French Teaching and Documentation (CFTD's) situated in the three zones of the three major ethnic groups of Nigeria have unified educational activities for the study of French. Thus the CFTD's at Jos, Enugu and Ibadan have the same projects executed at the same time at the three zones each year; such that French study activities are circulated within the country equally. The French government through its embassy here in Nigeria and through the Nigerian French Language Project is contributing immensely to the growth of French studies. Every year, there is always one project or another going on. For the concluded 2017 project, Durreisseix and Itodo (2017) noted: "For almost two years and a half, the Bilateral Co-operation Project lending support to French teaching in institutions of Higher Education in Nigeria has been on-going. It will end in November 2017...."

It is an established fact that primary education serves as a base for further and future studies. Children at this level socialize and integrate faster. With the study of foreign language and culture, they learn to tolerate cultural

differences and appreciate other people's culture. In so doing, it helps them mingle with other ethnic groups without much differences as they grow and develop.

Conclusion

That the federal government has made several positive statements that favour the study of French in Nigeria is no longer new information. But what matters is the implementation of such policies and declarations. If the government is serious about realizing its dreams for Nigerians to peak French, by introducing primary school curriculum, then French can be restored in the public primary schools like any other subjects for strong foundational studies. Primary school studies offer elementary and basic knowledge of subject areas. That is why it is very important to the growth of any nation. Nigeria should consider what goes on in the public primary school as foundation of solving educational problems by making sure that all mapped out primary curricula are fully and timely implemented.

The awareness of studies of French is created right from the basic school. It is a fact that many people are still ignorant about the potentials and benefits of French studies for both the individual and the larger society. When such is addressed, one can now see that French studies can act in the general progress

of national and international integration of Nigeria and Nigerians.

Recommendations

1. Since there is an existing primary school curriculum, French should be re-introduced to fully realize the object set out for the curriculum.
2. The study of French at this level is seen as a sensitizing study for those who would like to further their studies. Therefore, the study of French should begin at the primary school.
3. Primary school French competition should be introduced as we have in the secondary school level.
4. The French government should encourage primary school French as it does at the secondary and tertiary levels of education.
5. Teachers that studied French should be allowed to teach French in their schools of practice.
6. The State government should post and deploy all graduating French students to schools, especially those that read education and French.

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